

Replication of Indian Myths and Culture in Mulk Raj Anand's Short Stories: A Study Based on *Lajwanti and Other Stories*

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Abstract

Mulk Raj Anand is a well-known writer who contributed enormous works to Indian English Literature. He has used numerous elements of traditional Indian culture and myths in his short stories to highlight communal prejudice among the oppressed during the era of pre-independence. The collection of short stories Lajwanti and other stories is taken for this study focusing mainly on stories such as The Silver Bangles and A Village Wedding as they seem to be a warehouse of Indian myths that explore the themes of social inequality and the suffering of the marginalized community. These stories are the true witnesses of portraying the rich cultural and heritage value of our country. Anand tries to blend the traditional mythical elements of ancient India with contemporary storytelling. By incorporating proper cultural and mythical elements into the short stories, Anand connects his readers to a deeper level of understanding of the humanistic vision of modern India. The weaving of mythical concepts throughout his short stories helped him to make the readers more accessible to the history of ancient India and its culture. This paper investigates how the short stories of Mulk Raj Anand such as Lajwanti, The Silver Bangles and A Village Wedding utilize the mythical concepts of Indian culture to amalgamate the narrative techniques. This paper also explores how the narration helps the readers understand the complexity of tradition and modernity in the Indian context. Anand uses cultural motifs in his short stories to excavate the profound cultural heritage of India and at the same time, he offers a progressive and humanistic perspective on the social issues of contemporary society.

Keywords: Short Story, Narration, Culture, Mythology, Heritage, Human Perspective

Introduction

The renowned author of modern India, Mulk Raj Anand is well known for his intellectual works depicting traditional Indian myths and cultural values in his narratives. This paper focuses on his two famous short stories namely *Lajwanti*, *The Silver Bangles*, and *A Village Wedding*. He

attempts to portray the richness of our heritage, cultural values, folk history, beliefs, and rituals all through his short stories. Through these stories, he explores societal issues such as gender inequality, caste discrimination, and the sufferings of the marginalized community in the period of pre-independence. By incorporating proper cultural and mythical elements into the short stories, Anand connects his readers to a deeper level of understanding of the humanistic vision of modern India. The weaving of mythical concepts throughout his short stories helped him to make the readers more accessible to the history of ancient India and its culture.

Mulk Raj Anand is known for his intellectual use of literature as a tool for reforming contemporary society. His deep knowledge of Indian traditions and culture is proved in the portrayal of mythological concepts in his short stories such as *Lajwanti*, *The Silver Bangles* and *A Village Wedding*. These mythological and cultural components serve a purpose beyond only telling the story; they also emphasize Anand's profound respect for India's rich past. The author shows his deep connection with the myths, traditions, and practices that have long shaped the collective consciousness of the Indian people by deftly incorporating these traditional motifs into his novels. By doing this, he presents his writing as a "warehouse" of these cultural riches, utilizing fiction as a vehicle for upholding and spreading these enduring stories while also using them to further his political and social goals. The way in which Anand skillfully employs Indian mythology and cultural clichés in these two short stories is indicative of his wider literary style, which was greatly impacted by his exposure to European modernist and realist traditions when he was living in the United Kingdom. Although the author took cues from Western literary movements' narrative styles and subject concerns, she never wavered in her commitment to highlighting the distinct cultural and social realities of the Indian subcontinent. Anand's writing is characterized by this blending of Eastern and Western literary sensibilities; this is especially clear in the way he incorporates traditional Indian aspects into his stories to produce a unique, socially conscious storytelling style.

Furthermore, Anand's use of myths and cultural references in *The Silver Bangles* and *Lajwanti* can be seen as a deliberate strategy to make his critiques of the Indian social order more accessible and impactful. By tapping into the shared cultural knowledge and collective imagination of his readers, the author was able to create narratives that resonated on a deeper, more emotive level, allowing him to effectively challenge the oppressive customs and hierarchies that subjugated the vulnerable in pre-independence India. Mulk Raj Anand's short

stories exemplify the author's masterful integration of traditional Indian myths and cultural elements into his literary works. Anand employed fiction as a potent instrument to reveal the harsh realities experienced by the underprivileged in Indian society and to push for a more just and equitable social order, in addition to providing his readers with entertainment and education through these narratives. Anand positioned his novels as a "warehouse" of India's rich legacy by referencing a wide range of mythical and cultural motifs. He then used this cultural treasure to emphasize his progressive, humanist vision for the country.

Myth and Culture in *Lajwanti and Other Short Stories* of Mulk Raj Anand

Mulk Raj Anand talks about Indian myths and culture in many of his short stories and through these stories, he invites readers to reflect on the impact of these beliefs on individuals and communities. Numerous Indian myths and religious cultures are drawn in the short story *Lajwanti* written by Mulk Raj Anand. The psychological trauma faced by a woman in the period of the India-Pakistan partition has been portrayed using many mythological elements. Anand uses the mythical character Sita as a parallel to the central character of the story namely Lajwanti. Both characters face social ostracization from their society and they both face the same situation of abduction. The mythical flower "lajwanti" is used as a metaphor for the weak nature of women and how she is undervalued in society. His other popular story *The Silver Bangles* talks about the faith of the Hindu religion regarding the low-caste people who were considered an untouchable community. The servant girl was accused of the robbery of silver bangles only because she belongs to a low caste and also wearing a silver bangle. Shrimati, the one who blames the servant girl Sajini for stealing her bangle says,

“Don't you know that the low-caste people in the south are not supposed to wear silver ... you go posing like a cheap film star” (*The Silver Bangle* p.118).

The silver bangle is an imagery that represents both hope and superstition in society. The mythical elements that are used in the story to weave the day-to-day life of people in an Indian village reflect the deep-rooted beliefs and conventional rituals of the society. The villagers believe that the bangle has the power to ward off evil and bring good fortune. This belief is reflective of the broader cultural reliance on talismans and charms as a means of navigating the uncertainties of life. The bangle's hypothetical powers are not questioned by the villagers, highlighting the pervasive influence of superstition in their lives. The symbolism of

the silver bangle is depicted in the story not only to represent Sajani's hope for a future better life but also to trigger her husband's jealousy, which emphasizes the power of superstitions in ordinary lives. Mulk Raj Anand names his characters by choosing names from Indian mythology as a technique to portray the contrast between their names and nature. The husband of Sajani is named after the Lord Rama, as a symbol of uprightness and ethical values. However, his behavior toward the servant girl proves that he does not keep justice to his name. The family setting of Ram reminds us of the cultural influence in the stories of Mulk Raj Anand. The story reflects the power of the patriarchal culture of Indian society. The power of gender hierarchy is lucidly portrayed in the story as the relationship of the husband and wife in the story follows the male-dominated family setting.

Anand connects the culture and customs of Indian society in his other short story *A Village Wedding*. It is the story of an unsuccessful marriage that was stopped only because of the refusal of dowry by the bride's father. The marriage was stopped at the last moment when the bridegroom found out that he was not given any dowry and this situation was very embarrassing for the father of the bride. He decides to marry her to another boy who is from a low-caste community. The honour of the family was more important to the society than the life of the girl.

“Come, I will give my daughter in marriage to Kalu, Son of Bharty ... money lender has dragged into the mud” (*A Villlage Wedding* p.23).

The culture of dowry is highlighted in this story as it was believed to be incorrect by all the villagers and they had been following the dowry system for many years. They believed that the bride's father should be obliged to the son-in-law and he should give dowry as they do according to the Hindu mythology and beliefs.

The myth of Sati and Savitri is dealt with by Mulk Raj Anand in one of his stories namely *The Shadow of Death*. There was a custom among the people of India of the immolation of the wife herself in the funeral pyre of her husband. It was a religious funeral practice that insisted the widow burn herself along with her husband. Sati was a Hindu Goddess who self-immolated because of her father's humiliation towards her husband. The woman who follows the custom of Sati was named a chaste woman. However, the goddess Sati when she immolated, was not a widow. Hence, the myth was not that appropriate for the widows to practice immolation in

the husband's funeral pyre. The mythological women characters in the Indian myths who practised Sati were highly honoured and it is believed that that kind of woman can bless others for many future generations. Sati was honored in many places and temples were built for Sati in many places.

Savitri is the other well-known personality in Hindu mythology. She is the devoted wife of Satyavan and when the God of death came to take away the life of her husband, she requested to take her own life instead of her husband. But Yama, the God of death refused to do so. She followed Yama for a long distance begging the same. Gradually she lost her strength, but did not want to give up. Feeling compassion towards Savitri for her sincere and true love towards her husband, Yama promised her a boon instead of the life of her husband. She was permitted to ask anything except her husband's life. The intelligent devotee of her husband, Savitri asked the boon of having children from Satyavan. Yama, finally was forced to give the life of her husband back. These two mythological female characters Sati and Savitri were extremely devoted to their husbands and the Indian concept of 'wife' remains the same even after centuries.

The story of mythological characters Sati and Savitri is used by Mulk Raj Anand in *The Shadow of Death* to make the readers understand the depth of cultural values that Indians have been following since ancient times. The superstitious thoughts of the pre-independence period are revealed in his writings.

“You are blessed. Devi is calling you to be Sati ... You were named Savitri, Savitri of Satyug ... who defied death” (*The Shadow of Death* 2010).

Conclusion

The renowned writer Mulk Raj Anand has paved a remarkable pathway in the field of Indian English Literature with his masterful portrayal of Indian myths and culture in his stories. He tries to depict the lives of normal people in the period of the India-Pakistan partition after independence. His stories are powerful evidence for the social and political imbalance in the country and the patriarchal norms extremely followed in the society at that particular period of time. He delineates the hardships of women in the male-dominating society and uses his pen as a weapon to save the dignity and status of women in contemporary society. Mulk Raj Anand, in his short stories, tries to reveal the facts behind many of the rituals and customs on which

the Indians have huge faith. He tries to bring out the realities of the present Indian scenario and to bring about a transformation in Indian society. He has presented a huge picture of the traditions and culture of the country by portraying the mythical characters as big inspirations to the present generation.

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